

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		C	H	N	M
La ₃ L ₃ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Pale yellow	48.8 (49.1)	3.5 (3.6)	3.9 (4.0)	28.0 (28.2)
Nd ₃ L ₃	Pale yellow	51.4 (51.0)	2.6 (2.9)	4.4 (4.2)	28.3 (28.4)
Sm ₃ L ₃	Yellow	48.4 (48.3)	2.6 (2.8)	4.2 (4.3)	31.4 (31.0)
Gd ₃ L ₃ . ⁻ C ₂ H ₅ OH	Pale yellow	49.2 (49.6)	4.0 (3.8)	4.3 (4.1)	30.3 (30.2)
Dy ₃ L ₃ .2C ₂ H ₅ OH	Yellow	48.8 (49.0)	3.6 (3.7)	4.1 (4.0)	31.4 (31.0)
Ho ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	45.6 (45.9)	3.4 (3.4)	3.5 (4.1)	32.3 (32.2)
Er ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	44.6 (45.0)	3.5 (3.4)	3.8 (4.0)	32.3 (32.2)
Yb ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Pale yellow	43.9 (44.5)	3.3 (3.3)	3.6 (4.0)	32.5 (32.9)
Lu ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Pale yellow	44.9 (44.6)	3.5 (3.6)	4.0 (4.1)	33.4 (33.7)
Y ₃ L ₃ .4H ₂ O	Yellow	52.5 (53.0)	3.8 (3.9)	4.5 (4.8)	30.1 (30.1)

Results and Discussion

The ir and ¹H nmr spectra of LH₂ show evidence of strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding with the OH stretching vibration appearing as a broad band centred at 2 720 cm⁻¹ and with a broad signal at δ 9.65 \pm 0.1. The ir band at 3 450 cm⁻¹ and the signal at δ 7.1 \pm 0.1 are characteristics of the benzal OH group. The signals at δ 9.65 and 7.10 disappear on deuteration with D₂O. The azomethine proton exhibits a sharp signal at δ 8.75 and a sharp ir band at 3 065 cm⁻¹. Two absorption bands at 355 and 430 nm were observed in the electronic spectra of LH₂. They suffered a blue-shift on complexation indicating the covalent character of the metal-ligand bonds which increases as the atomic number increases. The correlation between the long wavelength band and the atomic number of the crystal radius gives excellent linear relationships for the metals beyond Gd^{III}. The presence of the water or ethanol molecules in these complexes is evident by a broad band at 3 400–3 500 cm⁻¹, the appearance of a medium to weak band at 2 920 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of ethanol in the ir spectra of the complexes and by the appearance of sharp signal at δ 3.4 \pm 0.05 in the nmr spectra of the complexes. The bands due to the OH group at 2 720 and 3 450, δ_{OH} at 1 370 and ν_{OH} at 940 cm⁻¹, disappear in the ir spectra of the complexes. The bands due to ν_{OH} , $\nu_{C=N}$ and ν_{C-N} shifted to shorter frequencies while $\nu_{C=O}$ shifted to higher frequency for the complexes than those observed in the ir spectrum of the ligand.

Also, both signals at δ 7.1 and 9.65 corresponding to the ligand OH groups disappear in the ¹H nmr spectra of the complexes of La^{III} and Lu^{III}. On the other hand, the signal due to the azomethine

proton slightly shifted up-field at δ 8.75–8.94. Thus, we can conclude that both OH groups and the nitrogen atom are involved in the coordination sphere.

The thermogravimetric study showed that the water and ethanol molecules in the complexes are coordinated to the lanthanide ion and are not just a part of the crystal lattice.

The molar conductances of 10⁻³ M solutions of the complexes in dimethyl formamide, nitrobenzene and nitromethane were in the range 70–87 Ω^{-1} cm² mol⁻¹. Thus, these complexes are strong electrolytes type⁵ under the experimental conditions used.

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Complexation of Dimethyltin(IV) Ion with 2-Mercaptopyridine-*N*-oxide and 8-Hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide

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IN continuation of our previous study on the complexation behaviour of dialkyltin(IV) ions¹ we report here the stability constants and related thermodynamic parameters of complex formation of dimethyltin(IV) ion with 2-mercaptopyridine-*N*-oxide and 8-hydroxyquinoline-*N*-oxide (hereafter 2MPNO and 8HQNO respectively) at 20, 30 and 40° in 75% (v/v) dioxan-water at a fixed ionic strength ($\mu=0.1M$).

Experimental

Experimental details of pH titration procedure are the same as described earlier¹. The ligands 2MPNO and 8HQNO (Aldrich) and dimethyltin dichloride (Alfa) were used. The acid dissociation constants of the ligands and formation constants of the complexes were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti². The thermodynamic para-

TABLE 1 - STEPWISE FORMATION CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Temp. °C	Formation constants		Thermodynamic formation constants		-ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	-ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁ ^o	log K ₂ ^o			
(H ₂ C) ₂ SnCl ₂ - 2MPNO	20	7.86	4.67	11.42	6.45	23.9	27.4	-12
	30	7.03	4.40	10.71	6.24			
	40	7.10	4.05	10.90	5.83			
(H ₂ C) ₂ SnCl ₂ - 8HQNO	20	9.72	9.13	13.28	10.91	32.4	20.3	43
	30	9.48	9.33	13.26	11.17			
	40	9.12	8.73	12.92	10.63			

TABLE 2 - ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.*	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
		Sn	S	C	H
(H ₂ C) ₂ Sn(C ₆ H ₄ NOS) ₂ (2MPNO)	195-96	30.2 (29.6)	16.6 (15.9)	37.1 (36.0)	3.7 (3.5)
(H ₂ C) ₂ Sn(C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂) ₂	210d	25.5 (25.3)	-	52.7 (51.1)	3.6 (3.8)

*2MPNO = C₆H₅NOS ; 8HQNO = C₆H₇NO₂.

mers and the stepwise formation constants (log K₁^o and log K₂^o) were calculated following the usual procedure³ (Table 1).

The solid complexes were isolated by adding 0.1N sodium hydroxide solution dropwise with constant stirring to a solution of dimethyltin dichloride and the respective chelating agent in 1:2 molar ratio in dioxan-water (75% v/v) till precipitation started. The dimethyltin(IV) complex with 2MPNO was a white solid (m.p. 195-96°), slightly soluble in chloroform and dichloromethane, whereas the corresponding complex with 8HQNO was a yellow solid, insoluble in all common organic solvents. The complex decomposed at 210°. Analytical data are presented in Table 2.

Results and Discussion

The experimental data in the pH range 2.5-6.5 were interpreted for the formation of 1:2 complexes. The formation curves for both the systems became flat at $\bar{n}=2$, indicating that the maximum number of ligands⁴ that can be coordinated in the dioxan-water medium is 2. The higher stability of dimethyltin dichloride-8HQNO complexes than those of 2MPNO complexes is in accord with the earlier report of Tobias and Yasuda⁵ that dimethyltin(IV) ion being a typical hard acid forms quite stable complexes with oxygen donors. This is also in accord with our earlier observation that in complexes of dimethyltin(IV) ion with amino acids, there is weak bonding between the ion and oxygen donors. The negative values of ΔG in both the systems indicate the spontaneity of com-

plexation reactions. The positive ΔS value for the complexation of 8HQNO with dimethyltin(IV) ion indicates that complex formation in this system is favoured by enthalpic as well as entropic contributions. For the system involving 2MPNO, ΔS value is negative indicating that formation of complexes is strongly driven by enthalpic forces.

Ir bands observed in these bis-complexes at 1055-1102 cm⁻¹ due to N⁺-O⁻ stretching at lower frequencies on complexation indicated the coordination of the N-O group^{4,6}. The bands at 530-540 and 560-570 cm⁻¹ could be assigned respectively to ν_{Sn-O} and ν_{Sn-O}⁷. In case of the 2MPNO complex, the band at 355 cm⁻¹ was assigned¹ to ν_{Sn-S}. The pmr spectrum (CDCl₃) of the 2MPNO complex displayed a multiplet due to pyridine protons in the range δ 6.9-8.1 and Me-(Sn) signal at δ 1.0. This further showed ²J¹¹⁹Sn-Me value to be ca 80 Hz corresponding to six-coordinate tin⁸. The presence of only one (Sn-C) absorption in the ir spectra cannot be taken as final evidence for *cis* or *trans* orientation of the methyl groups. ¹³C nmr spectrum of the complex exhibited one resonance at δ 158.1 ppm due to C(S), four resonances at δ 138.1, 130.8, 130.1 and 118.4 ppm due to the other pyridine carbon atoms and one resonance at δ 10.2 ppm due to carbon of methyl groups attached to the tin⁹.

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Stability of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Cadmium with some Amino Acids and Propionic Acid. A Polarographic Study

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IN continuation of previous work¹⁻³, the present study aims to find out the stability of binary and ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and propionic acid as secondary ligand by polarographic technique.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions in conductivity water. The concentrations of metal ion, potassium nitrate and gelatin in the test solution are 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. The purities of amino acids were checked by chromatographic method⁴ and the concentration of each amino acid varied in the range 1.0–10.0 mM.

The metal and ligands (amino acid and propionic acid) were taken in the ratio 1 : 40 and current-voltage curves were drawn. The maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was observed at pH 8.50 \pm 0.1 and hence this pH was selected for the investigation.

Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal pL-50 polyflex galvanometer. The capillary characteristics were $n^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.0 cm (60.02 calculated)⁵ effective height of mercury. Nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions for deoxygenation before recording the current-voltage measurements. An Elico LI-10 needle type pH-meter was used to measure the pH which was adjusted at 8.50 \pm 0.1 with dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and nitric acid as required. All the measurements were made at 25 \pm 0.1°. Stability constants were calculated by Lingane⁶ and Deford and Hume⁷ methods.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} gave a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in KNO₃ and gelatin⁸. All the waves for the metal and its complexes were reversible and diffusion-controlled which were confirmed from the plots of $E_{d,e}$ vs $\log(i/i_a - i)$ and i_d vs \sqrt{h} , respectively.

Cd propionate system: The system was studied at pH 8.50 \pm 0.1 and $I=1.0 \text{ M}$ (KNO₃). All the waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled which were confirmed from $(E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}) = 30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ values and also the plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs $E_{d,e}$ and i_d vs \sqrt{h} , respectively. Lingane⁶ treatment of the data confirmed the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with stability constants $\log \beta_{01} = 2.46$ and $\log \beta_{02} = 3.90$ respectively.

Cd-amino acid-propionic acid system: This system was also studied at pH = 8.50 \pm 0.1 by keeping the concentration of propionic acid constant at 0.005 and 0.01 M while varying the concentration of each amino acid from 1.0 to 10.0 mM, and current-voltage curves were obtained. The values of $E_{1/2}$ increased with increase of the concentration of amino acid showing complexes formation for each of the constant concentration of propionic acid. The values of pK and stability of binary and ternary complexes⁸ of Cd^{II} with amino acids and propionic and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II}

System	pK ₂ ^H	pK ₁ ^H	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
[Cd-gly.-prop.]	2.40	9.30	4.30	7.60	9.64	6.56	8.97	9.37
[Cd- α -ala.-prop.]	2.50	9.40	4.23	7.46	9.43	6.40	8.75	9.15
[Cd-L-val.-prop.]	2.28	9.71	4.11	7.21	9.16	6.38	8.60	8.97
[Cd-L-leu.-prop.]	2.32	9.74	4.17	7.35	9.34	6.22	8.38	8.75
[Cd-L-glut.-prop.]	2.17	9.13	4.00	7.04	8.91	6.21	8.31	8.67
[Cd-L-asp.-prop.]	2.02	8.80	4.07	7.18	9.10	6.05	8.09	8.45